

MODERN APPROACHES TO TEACHING ENGLISH PRIMARY SCHOOLS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6573702>

Saparova Gulzor Khudoyorovna

Teacher of school No. 2 of

Tuprakkala district of Khorezm region

Abstract: *This article conducts research on the implementation of new projects and approaches in the teaching of a foreign language, ie English, which is currently important to learn.*

Keywords: *Country, education, purpose, interactive approaches, modern foreign language.*

INTRODUCTION.

In our country, the social order of society has further strengthened the need for the teaching of foreign languages in primary school for communicative purposes. English was introduced as a subject in primary education, training of specialists in the field of teaching foreign languages in preschool and primary education was organized.

One of the main and positive changes is the Resolution of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 No PP-1875 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages." Based on this decision, the study of foreign languages, mainly English, in the form of game-based lessons and oral lessons from the 1st grade of general secondary schools, and from the 2nd grade, the alphabet, reading and grammar training begins in stages. According to the resolution, under the leadership of the Coordinating Council, which is constantly working to further develop the study of foreign languages, began to carry out unprecedented work in all areas of education. For example, starting from the 2013-2014 academic year, continuous teaching of foreign languages in the form of games and oral lessons has been introduced in the first grades of secondary schools. Textbooks and teaching aids for these classes have also been created. It is noteworthy that the activities in the complexes created for the first grades are proportional to the age of the little ones. Children began their first acquaintance with a foreign language by learning the culture of greeting, colors, and everyday words in the form of dialogue.

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE SUBJECT.

• Perceptions serve as the main analyzer in the reading process, and auditory perceptions in listening comprehension. Oral speech serves as listening material, and written speech serves as reading material. With regard to the relationship of listening comprehension to speaking, listening comprehension and speaking are inextricably linked. But there are also features that distinguish them. The main role in the process of

listening comprehension is played by the auditory analyzer, and the motor and visual analyzers play a supporting role. In the process of speaking, the main role is played by motor analyzers. In this sense, listening comprehension and speaking are interrelated. Teaching English To Students in Elementary School What you should be aware of before you begin. Prepared by Abdulrahman Gadah Abdulrahman Gadah What's in an ideal course book? Learning through the senses. Chants. Games 4. Writing 5. Variety of text types (up-to-date). Cross-curricular information 7. Cultural information 8. Activities which practise the four skills / Language in context 9. Projects 10. Self-evaluation section 11. Phonics activities 12. Based on a theory / approach 13. Interactive Whiteboard material 14. A clear Teachers Manual 15. Flashcards 4. 1. How do we learn? 1. How do we learn? Through our senses. 5. We primarily learn through sight. Attractive pictures Up-to-date themes 6. We primarily learn through sight. Attractive pictures Up-to-date themes 7. 2. Chants 8. 2. Chants 9. 3. Games 10. 3. Games 11. 4. Writing 12. 4. Writing 13. Factual Texts 5. A variety of text types 14. Stories 5. A variety of text types 15. What is the value of cross-curricular texts? Topic engage Ss interest. Help reinforce or revise knowledge about the real world. Allows for a more spherical approach to learning. Allows even weak Ss at English to contribute sth. 6. Cross-curricular texts.

Listening comprehension can be done in a variety of situations. The main content of the methodology of speech development is the organization of organizational pedagogical and methodological work on the development of oral speech in children, its children's speech. Improving the level of speech correction in the development of speech in preschool adults is one of the main tasks before the methodologists of the preschool education system. With this in mind, it is advisable to start the research on the problem of speech development of older children of preschool age in the study of the environment by identifying the factors that ensure speech development. For example, in direct communication with the interlocutor, in training sessions, in the theater, listening to the radio, talking on the phone, and so on. High school is faced with the task of developing the teacher's ability to understand speech on a topic of everyday life that is focused on the student or class or recorded on a magnetic button in a much simpler direct interaction process. If the reader hears the information and knows its general content as well as some details, it can be considered that he has understood the text. It is not necessary to understand every word or phrase. Thus, teaching listening comprehension in high school is done as follows.

CONCLUSION

The feature of teaching English for primary school is as follows: it is essential to note again that the most effective way to teach English in primary school is game technology as well as a variety of picture cards. This is the first step in a great development to the establishment of the English language from primary school. It is not

in vain that our ancestors said that knowledge gained from youth is a pattern carved in stone. We will achieve our goal if we increase our children's interest in English from primary school and pay special attention to vocabulary. For example, in primary schools, students are required to be able to understand stories based on oral material. From secondary school, students are given texts with some unfamiliar words for listening comprehension. The volume of the received texts is increased from class to class by 0.5-1 minutes

REFERENCES:

1. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 No PP-1875 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages."

1. 2.Iriskulov AT and others Kids' English pupil's book 2nd grade - Tashkent —Uzbekistan; 2014

2. 3.Passov Ye.I. Kommunikativniy metod obucheniya inoyazichnomu govoreniyu. M .: Prosveshchenie, 1991

3. Xoshimov O '. Yakubov I. Methods of teaching English. T., - 2003